

COMPETITIVENESS OF THE BULGARIAN MINING INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT. The report presents the state of competitiveness of the Bulgarian economy, the Industry sector and the Mining and Quarrying subsector for the period 2018-2024. The change in key quantitative indicators characterising competitiveness at the level of the national economy, the Industry sector and the Mining and Quarrying subsector is analysed. The aim of this study is to outline the state of competitiveness of the Bulgarian mining industry in the period 2018-2024 through an analysis of the available sectoral and national statistical information. The results substantiate that in the period 2018-2024, the Bulgarian mining industry raised its economic results, labour productivity, personnel remuneration, and competitiveness.

Key words: Bulgarian mining industry, competitiveness, sector analysis.

КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТ НА БЪЛГАРСКАТА МИННА ИНДУСТРИЯ **Веселин Митев, Йоан Христов, Антонио Черчеланов, Елица Арсова** *Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София*

РЕЗЮМЕ. В доклада е представено състоянието на конкурентността на българската икономика, на сектор „Индустрия“ и на подсектор „Добивна промишленост“ за периода 2018 – 2024 г. Анализирани са измененията на ключови количествени показатели, характеризиращи конкурентността на равнище национална икономика, сектор „Индустрия“ и подсектор „Добивна промишленост“. Целта на настоящото изследване е чрез анализ на наличната браншова и национална статистическа информация да се очертае състоянието на конкурентността на българската минна индустрия през периода 2018 – 2024 г. Резултатите обосновават, че през периода 2018 – 2024 г. българската минна индустрия повишава икономическите си резултати, производителността на труда, заплащането на персонала и конкурентоспособността.

Ключови думи: българска минна индустрия, конкурентоспособност, секторен анализ.

Introduction

Michael Porter was the first to introduce the category of “competitiveness” at the industry, corporate, and business levels (Porter, 1980). In his later works, he further developed his theory of competitiveness (Porter, 2003, 2009). Other authors, such as (Chursin & Makarov, 2015), accept it as a complex category, without being an economic conceptual category, due to its use as a generalising concept at different levels (national, regional, industry, company, product), as well as due to the use of different values and indicators for its measurement.

On the other hand, according to Siderova (2013), “Competitiveness is an overall measure of the economic development of any system of economy and summarises the effectiveness of the functioning of its economic, sectoral, social, financial, government, and other subsystems”.

Competitiveness reveals the ability of economic entities to increase national, sectoral, and individual productivity and to compete with other entities at, respectively, global, regional, sectoral, and company level.

At the level of the national economy, competitiveness is manifested in many directions, namely: the potential for sustainable growth with its inherent three pillars – economic, social, and environmental. Economic competitiveness must combine with sustainable development, thus, with the rational and efficient use of the natural resources of a national economy (Dogaru, 2020; Ikram & Sayagh, 2023).

According to the definition of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 1996, as cited in Garelli, 2002), a nation's competitiveness is “the degree to which a country can, under free and fair market conditions, produce goods and services that meet the test of international markets, while simultaneously maintaining and expanding the real

incomes of its people in the long term”. This definition includes the following three major conditions:

1. The ability of the economy to meet international requirements.
2. Free market and trade.
3. Real incomes do not increase within a long period.

Unfortunately, specialised literature has not clarified the concept of “competitiveness” at the industry level in terms of specific indicators by which it can be determined.

Research data and methods

The methods used in the development of this study are: research of scientific literature and statistical information, analysis and synthesis, systemic approach, the method of inter-economy comparisons, and graphical methods for time series analysis.

The aim of this study is to outline the state of competitiveness of the Bulgarian mining industry during the period 2018-2024 through an analysis of industry and national statistical information available.

The sources of information for the study are: national and international databases with scientific information, statistical data of the National Statistical Institute of the Republic of Bulgaria, its INFOSTAT information system, the Ministry of Economy, and the Ministry of Energy.

Competitiveness of the Bulgarian economy

According to the renowned global competitiveness ranking for 2024 of the Institute for Management Development (IMD), Switzerland, Bulgaria is ranked among the 67 countries with less than 20 million population. In the ranking, this country is lagging behind from 48th place in 2020 to 58th place in 2024 in terms of

the overall implementation of the four main groups of criteria, including a total of 20 such criteria, presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Global competitiveness ranking for Bulgaria by criteria groups for 2024.

Indicator	Ranking position
Economic Performance	
Domestic Economy	48
International Trade	28
International Investment	59
Employment	56
Prices	9
Government Efficiency	
Public Finance	43
Tax Policy	24
Institutional Framework	54
Business Legislation	62
Societal Framework	57
Business Efficiency	
Productivity & Efficiency	57
Labour Market	67
Finance	53
Management Practices	61
Attitudes & Values	64
Infrastructure	
Basic Infrastructure	65
Technological Infrastructure	54
Scientific Infrastructure	54
Health & Environment	53
Education	52

Source: per data from the Institute for Management Development, compiled by the authors. https://imd.widen.net/content/ma2a4k34pb/pdf/BG1page_WCY_2024.pdf.

The data in Table 1 shows that the most serious lag is in the following criteria: labour market; attitudes and values; basic infrastructure; management practices; business legislation; international investment; productivity and efficiency. These areas need to be a particular priority for the Bulgarian government when developing strategies and policies for the sustainable development of the Bulgarian economy.

Fig. 1 presents the change in real GDP of the World, American, European, and Bulgarian economic systems in the period 2018 – 2024, along with and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) forecast for 2025 and 2026.

The data in Fig. 1 show that Bulgaria's national economy maintains a higher real GDP growth than the EU economy, is close to that of the US, and is inferior to the Chinese and global economies. The forecasts for the development of the EU economy are highly pessimistic; for years, two-thirds of the Bulgarian commerce has been with the countries of Central and Southern Europe. This determines Bulgaria's strong dependence on the situation in Europe. Of course, the economic environment is highly dynamic and is affected by significant economic and political shocks.

* - IMF estimates

Fig 1. Change in the real GDP of the World, American, European and Bulgarian economic systems during the period 2018-2024 and forecasts for 2025 and 2026.

Source: per IMF. World Economic Outlook. (2019=2025); compiled by the authors.

Fig. 2 presents Bulgaria's gross domestic product (GDP) at current prices and at 2020 prices according to INFOSTAT data for the period 2018-2024.

The data in Fig. 2 shows that for the period 2018–2024, the Bulgarian economy achieved an average sustainable real growth of 2.6% per year. The exception is 2020, when the anti-epidemiological measures were the most restrictive, which led

to a decline in consumption and economic activity both on a national and global scale. The Bulgarian economy contracted by 4.4% then. Linear regression models of the time series of Bulgaria's GDP at current prices and at 2020 prices are derived. These are characterised by very high determination coefficients

(R^2). This justifies a very high degree of predictability of the indicators based on a retrospective period. Of course, such forecasts are significantly influenced by the occurrence of significant changes in the micro- and macroeconomic environment.

Fig. 2. Gross domestic product of Bulgaria at current prices and at 2020 prices.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors. https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=1169

Competitiveness of the Industry Sector (excluding Construction)

Fig. 3 shows the gross value added (GVA) per basic prices for Bulgaria and for the Industry sector (excluding Construction) according to INFOSTAT data for the period 2018-2024.

The data in Fig. 3 show that the Industry sector (excluding Construction) achieved sustainable real growth in GVA for the

period 2018–2024 of 14.1% on average per year. Bulgaria's gross value added achieved sustainable real growth for the period 2018–2024 of 14.3% on average per year. For the period 2018 –2024, the relative share of sector “Industry (excluding Construction)” in Bulgaria's GVA changed from 21.4% in 2018 to 21.3% in 2024. The derived linear regression models of the time series of the GVA of the Industry sector (excluding Construction) and of Bulgaria are again characterised by very high coefficients of determination.

Fig. 3. GVA per basic prices for Bulgaria and for the Industry sector (excluding Construction) for the period 2018-2024.

Source: based on data from "INFOSTAT", compiled by the authors. https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=135

Competitiveness of the Mining and Quarrying Subsector

According to information officially published by the National Statistical Institute (NSI) and data from the INFOSTAT information system of the NSI, the Ministry of Economy, and the Ministry of Energy, presented in Table 2, a large part of the

Bulgarian mining enterprises currently achieve high production and economic results.

The data presented in Table 2 show that in the period 2018–2024, the subsector of Mining and Quarrying Industry developed sustainably and at an increasing pace with slight fluctuations.

Table 2. Main economic indicators of the Bulgarian mining industry for the period 2018 ÷ 2023.

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Number of enterprises, num.	368	343	350	338	336	315
Number of persons employed, num.	21522	19022	20084	19406	18700	18666
Production value, BGN'000.	2759501	2586650	3097435	3713231	4306251	n.a.
Turnover, BGN'000.	2708557	2410071	3016884	3604437	3996061	n.a.
Wages and salaries, BGN'000.	454973	415738	483440	525294	575655	n.a.
Personnel costs, BGN'000.	603185	559309	637403	525294	571983	n.a.
Value of tangible fixed assets, BGN'000	2474027	2525260	2436826	1759214	1798815	1381536
Operating income, BGN'000.	2981356	2727440	3341833	4012363	5536084	4602496
Operating expenses, BGN '000.	2562865	2569378	2637844	3009184	4620868	38028720
Financial result from operating activities, BGN '000	418491	158062	703989	1003179	915216	799624
Value added at factor costs, BGN '000.	1345218	1277034	1790034	2044514	1911332	n.a.
Export of mining production, € '000.	3287707	3848548	2293456	3017475	7059375	5057451
Import of mining production, € '000.	6364848	6136746	4579977	6041212	12169804	5657451

Source: The table is based on INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.

https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/query.jsf?x_2=567

https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/query.jsf?x_2=250

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Table 3 presents the industrial production indices for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying subsector, in total and by activities, calendar-adjusted to 2021.

The data in Table 3 show that, overall, the industrial production indices of the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector lagged behind the industrial production indices of the Industry sector throughout the period. As a result of the

economic crisis, a significant decline in the industrial production indices in 2020 was observed for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector, and for the "Coal Mining" activity. During the analysed period, only "Mining of Non-Metallic Minerals and Raw Materials" remained stable.

Table 3. Industrial production indices for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry sub-sector, in total and by activity (calendar-adjusted to 2021 = 100%)

Indicator	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total	98.6	97.1	91.1	100.0	113.3	103.8	100.1
Mining and quarrying	87.1	91.5	90.0	100.0	108.6	93.8	89.6
Mining of coal and lignite	95.0	95.0	75.4	100.0	131.9	71.3	48.4
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores	91.8	97.7	103.5	100.0	98.0	109.3	106.9
Other mining and quarrying	69.1	73.1	76.7	100.0	100.7	92.8	88.8
Mining support service activities

Note: Data for the activities of "Oil and Natural Gas Extraction" and "Ancillary Activities in Extraction" are confidential because there are less than four companies.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.

https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=2299

Table 4 presents the turnover indices in industry for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector in total and by activities, calendar-adjusted to 2021.

The data in Table 4 show that only in 2020, in general, the turnover industry indices in Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector were ahead of the Industry sector turnover indices, while significantly lagging behind in other periods. For the period

2018-2024, the mining industry realised extremely high dynamics of the turnover indices in the industry. According to this indicator, the industry underwent a series of ups and downs. Only coal mining remained relatively stable; however, since 2023 it has already shown a trend of significant decline. In the period 2022-2024, the mining of non-metallic raw materials was the most sustainable in growth.

Table 4. Turnover indices in industry for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector in total and by activities (calendar-adjusted to 2021 = 100%)

Indicator	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total	78.9	81.5	75.5	100.0	156.8	123.9	121.5
Mining and quarrying	63.3	70.7	76.8	100.0	107.7	92.1	92.8
Mining of coal and lignite	105.9	99.9	79.8	100.0	137.0	80.9	65.3
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores	62.5	69.7	80.7	100.0	97.7	83.5	89.2
Other mining and quarrying	60.9	66.6	71.7	100.0	121.4	132.7	127.9
Mining support service activities

Note: Data for the activities of "Oil and Natural Gas Extraction" and "Ancillary Activities in Extraction" are confidential because there are less than four companies.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.

https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=2302

Table 5 presents the turnover indices on the domestic market and on the international market in industry for the

Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector, in total and by activities, calendar-adjusted to 2021.

Table 5. Turnover indices on the domestic market and on the international market in industry for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector, in total and by activities (calendar-adjusted to 2021 = 100%).

Turnover indexes on domestic market in industry	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total	74.9	76.5	71.8	100.0	163.11	121.4	117.7
Mining and quarrying	68.7	70.5	73.2	100.0	113.2	110.3	111.0
Mining of coal and lignite	105.9	99.5	79.8	100.0	137.0	80.9	65.4
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores	62.6	64.3	72.8	100.0	102.8	110.3	117.45
Other mining and quarrying	62.0	66.2	69.0	100.0	110.9	135.1	135.6
Mining support service activities
Turnover indexes on non domestic market in industry	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total	85.2	89.1	81.2	100.0	147.0	127.6	127.3
Mining and quarrying	46.9	71.7	88.1	100.0	88.8	38.4	27.1
Mining of coal and lignite
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores	62.1	86.8	105.2	100.0	81.5	0.0	0.0
Other mining and quarrying	56.4	68.6	83.5	100.0	125.3	117.8	102.8
Mining support service activities

Note: Data for the activities of "Coal Mining", "Oil and Natural Gas Extraction", and "Ancillary Activities in Extraction" are confidential because there are less than four companies.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.

https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=2303

https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=2304

The data in Table 5 show that, in general, the turnover indices on the domestic market of the Mining Industry subsector are lower than those of the Industry sector. The mining industry has achieved constant growth, with a slight decline of 2.9% in 2023. In 2022, record coal production was recorded, followed by a significant decline in 2023 and 2024. A trend of constant growth has become evident in the mining of metal ores and non-metallic minerals and raw materials. The turnover indices on the domestic market have been higher than those on the international market, which indicates that mining production is

primarily directed to the domestic market. On the international market, the turnover indices of the Mining Industry subsector have been significantly lower than have been those of the Industry sector.

An interesting fact is that from September 2022 to the end of 2024, the turnover indices on the international market for the mining of metal ores were zero.

Table 6 presents the general manufacturer price indices in the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector, in total and by activities, calendar-adjusted to 2021.

Table 6. General manufacturer price indices in the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector, in total and by activities (calendar-adjusted to 2021 = 100%)

Indicator	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total	98.6	88.5	86.7	100.0	137.3	124.9	121.3
Mining and quarrying	80.0	81.1	85.6	100.0	109.2	110.1	121.6
Mining of coal and lignite	110.2	104.3	104.4	100.0	104.3	119.7	134.8
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores	69.1	70.1	76.6	100.0	104.3	99.0	111.7
Other mining and quarrying	91.1	93.1	96.1	100.0	123.4	140.7	146.7
Mining support service activities

Note: Data for the activities of "Oil and Natural Gas Extraction", and "Ancillary Activities in Extraction" are confidential because there are less than four companies.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.
https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=1102

The data in Table 6 show that, with the exception of 2024, the overall manufacturer price indices of the Industry sector have been higher than those of the Mining and Quarrying subsector. In the mining industry, a steady growth of the overall manufacturer price indices has been observed. Only in 2023 was a decline observed in the prices of mined out metal ores. The extracted non-metallic minerals and raw materials have

seen the highest average annual price increase. In 2024, a significant growth of 34.8% in the prices of the mined coal was also reported.

Table 7 presents the manufacturer price indices on the domestic market and on the international market in industry for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying subsector, in total and by activities (calendar-adjusted to 2021 = 100%)

Table 7. Manufacturer price indices on the domestic market and on the international market in industry for the Industry sector, the Mining and Quarrying subsector, in total and by activities (calendar-adjusted to 2021 = 100%)

Producer price indexes on the domestic market in industry	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total	84.0	87.2	87.0	100.0	148.4	129.9	123.6
Mining and quarrying	84.5	82.9	84.4	100.0	112.6	114.1	123.4
Mining of coal and lignite	110.2	104.3	104.3	100.0	104.4	119.8	134.9
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores	74.2	69.8	72.6	100.0	109.0	104.1	113.0
Other mining and quarrying	92.9	95.0	96.3	100.0	120.6	136.2	144.1
Mining support service activities
Producer price indexes on non-domestic market	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry – Total I	88.6	90.3	86.2	100.0	121.2	117.7	117.9
Mining and quarrying	62.0	73.9	90.6	100.0	95.7	93.8	114.3
Mining of coal and lignite
Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
Mining of metal ores
Other mining and quarrying	85.4	86.2	95.5	100.0	133.4	156.8	155.8
Mining support service activities

Note: Data for the activities of "Coal Mining", "Oil and Natural Gas Extraction", "Metal Ore Mining", and "Ancillary Activities in Mining" are confidential because there are less than four companies.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.
https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=1107
https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/result.jsf?x_2=1330

The data in Table 7 show that, in general, the manufacturer price indices on the domestic market are higher than the manufacturer price indices on the international market. The exception is the manufacturer price indices on the international

market for the extraction of non-metallic minerals and raw materials: those have seen the highest growth rates.

Table 8 presents the GDP and GVA per employee for Bulgaria – in total, the GVA per employee for the Industry sector, and value added (VA) by factor costs per employee for the

Mining and Quarrying subsector at current prices in BGN. Labour productivity in the Mining subsector for the period 2018-2024 has been calculated in two variants based on INFOSTAT

information about realised revenues from the activity and VA at factor costs, related to the number of employees in the subsector, previously presented in Table 2.

Table 8. GDP and GVA per employee for Bulgaria – in total, GVA per employee for the Industry sector, and VA by factor costs per employee for the Mining and Quarrying subsector at current prices

Indicator	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
GDP per employee – Bulgaria as a whole, BGN per employed person.	31174	34578	35550	40958	48879	53206	57653
GVA per employed person – Bulgaria total, BGN per employed person.	24790	27503	28584	33439	40771	43730	47746
GVA per employee – "Industry" total, BGN per employed person.	27155	28816	30585	33259	49438	48943	53297
Income from the activity of one employee for the subsector "Extractive industry", BGN per employed person	138526	143383	166393	206759	294473	246473	n.a.
VA at factor costs per employee for the "Extractive Industry" subsector, BGN per person employed.	62504	67135	89127	105355	101667	n.a.	n.a.

Source: per INFOSTAT data, compiled by the authors.

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https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/query.jsf?x_2=789
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https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/reports/query.jsf?x_2=1947

Unlike GDP, the calculation of GVA measures the result of production at basic prices, before the assessment of taxes, including subsidies on products and services. For this reason, GVA is lower than GDP. Unfortunately, at the level of the Mining and Quarrying subsector, the GDP and GVA indicators are not determined. For this reason, the labour productivity of the subsector can only be represented by the indicators of "Revenues per employee" and of "VA by factor costs per employee".

The data in Table 8 show that the revenue per employee in the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector grew from 138,526 BGN per employee in 2018 to 246,473 BGN per employee in 2023, which was an increase of 107,947 BGN per employee, or a 77.9% rise. The VA on factor costs per employee in the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector grew from 62,504 BGN per employee in 2018 to 101,667 BGN per employee in 2022. The growth was 39,163 BGN per employee, or 62.7%. This was an average annual growth of 15.7%.

Conclusion

According to the renowned competitiveness ranking for 2024 of the Institute for Management Development, Switzerland, for the period 2020-2024, Bulgaria has lagged behind from 48th to 58th place. The most serious lag is in the following criteria: international investment; employment; labour market; attitudes and values; basic infrastructure; management practices; business legislation; productivity, and efficiency. These areas need to be a priority for the Bulgarian government.

Bulgaria's national economy maintains a higher real GDP growth than the EU economy, is close to that of the US, and is inferior to the Chinese and global economies.

In the period 2018-2024, the Bulgarian economy marked a sustainable real growth of 2.6% on average per year. The derived linear regression models of the time series of Bulgaria's GDP at current prices and at 2020 prices justify a very high

degree of predictability of the indicators based on a retrospective period.

The Industry sector (excluding Construction) achieved sustainable real growth in GVA for the period 2018–2024 of 14.1% on average per year. Bulgaria's gross value added achieved sustainable real growth for the period 2018–2024 of 14.3% on average per year. For the period 2018–2024, the relative share of sector "Industry (excluding Construction)" in Bulgaria's GVA changed from 21.4% in 2018 to 21.3% in 2024.

For the period 2018-2024, the industrial production indices, industrial turnover indices, turnover indices on the domestic and international market, general producer price indices, and domestic and international manufacturer price indices of the Mining and Quarrying sub-sector generally lagged behind the analogous indices of the Industry sector throughout the period.

For the period 2018-2024, the Bulgarian mining industry achieved extremely high dynamics, which indicates that the industry went through a series of ups and downs with a growth trend.

The revenue per employee in the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector grew from 138,526 BGN per employee in 2018 to 246,473 BGN in 2023. This was an increase of 107,947 BGN (or 77.9%) per employee, or a rise of 15.6% per year.

The indicator of VA per factor costs per employee in the Mining and Quarrying Industry subsector grew from 62,504 BGN per employee in 2018 to 101,667 BGN per employee in 2022. The growth was by 39,163 BGN (or 62.7%) per employee, which was an average annual growth of 15.7%.

In the period 2018-2024, the Bulgarian mining industry increased its economic performance, labour productivity, personnel remuneration, and competitiveness.

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